

OPPORTUNITIES FOR APPLYING A COGNITIVE APPROACH IN ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN THE ACADEMIC LYCEUMS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS

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Annotation. The article presents proposals and recommendations on organizing the independent learning activities of students in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on the basis of a cognitive approach.

Keywords: cognitive approach, independent learning activities, academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, students, methodological approaches.

In modern pedagogical processes, the development of students' intellectual activity, the consolidation of knowledge, and the formation of skills to apply them in practice are recognized as one of the most pressing tasks. The cognitive approach stands at the center of this process, focusing on the activation of such mental processes as perception, memory, thinking, and logical reasoning. This approach not only limits itself to providing ready-made knowledge to students, but also encourages them to engage in independent learning, substantiate their own opinions, as well as analyze and synthesize information [1].

In this regard, that is, research related to the methodology of organizing independent learning activity in the system of continuous education on the basis of the cognitive approach has been studied by such scientists as V.V. Bayluk, Sh.Ye. Kazaryan, A.E. Grigoryan, M. Glotova, T. Petukhova, A.D. Deykina, S.I. Makarov, S.A. Sevastyanova, Y.A. Savitskiy, L.I. Ufimseva, V.N. Yakovleva, U.M. Mirsanov, M.A. Pazilov, V.R. Ochilova. According to the opinion of the scientists whose names are mentioned above, integrating the cognitive approach into the educational process in the system of continuous education makes it possible for students not only to deeply master theoretical knowledge, but also to form analytical thinking, quick decision-making and a responsible approach that will be necessary in their future professional activities.

In particular, according to U.M. Mirsanov, "The systemic approach is based on analyzing phenomena as a whole system. This approach is directed to identifying the components in the studied object and their interrelations, as well as to uniting them on a general theoretical basis. According to the analysis of scientific sources, the

main concepts of the systemic approach are system, structure and environment” [2]. According to the statement of V.N. Yakovleva, from the point of view of the theory of systemic approach, the following interrelated functions are distinguished in teaching: purposeful, informational, forecasting, decision-making, organizational, communicative, control-evaluative and corrective [3]. Also, according to the statement of Y.A. Savitskiy, the formation of students’ independent working skills is realized not only by giving separate tasks, but also through the construction of the entire educational process on a strictly systematized basis.

In this, the systemic approach is characterized through the following components: independent works should be an integral part of the curriculum and must be harmonized with other elements of education; educational tasks must be closely related to the knowledge previously acquired by the student and the competencies that need to be acquired in the future; independent works should be organized in a logical sequence, in a way where the degree of difficulty increases; in performing independent work, students are guided through necessary instructions, criteria and intermediate assessment tools [4].

In our opinion, through organizing the independent learning activity of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on the basis of the systemic approach, skills of activity orientation, independent thinking, self-assessment and self-management are developed in students.

On the basis of the analysis of the research of scientists related to the field and our investigations, it became known that relying on the cognitive approach in organizing the independent learning activity of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs provides the following opportunities (see Table 1).

Table 1

The following opportunities of relying on the cognitive approach in organizing the independent learning activity of students of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

№	Opportunities	Content
1.	Constructing meaningful knowledge	With the help of cognitive strategies (analysis, synthesis, concept maps), students actively form knowledge.
2.	Development of analytical and reflective thinking	“Based on real-life practical situations, students develop the skills to analyze cause-and-effect relationships and to evaluate alternative decisions.”

3.	Development of independent research competencies	Skills of searching, selecting, evaluating information and drawing scientifically grounded conclusions are strengthened.
4.	Metacognitive self-management	Through planning the learning process, monitoring, evaluating results and correction, self-management is developed.
5.	Cooperative learning activity	Self-management is developed through planning the learning process, monitoring, evaluating outcomes, and making adjustments
6.	Integration of ICT (Information and Communication Technologies)	Knowledge is integrated with practical activities through interactive resources, virtual simulations, and case-study methods.

Thus, organizing independent learning activity in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on the basis of the cognitive approach forms students' skills of meaningful knowledge construction, analytical and reflective thinking, metacognitive management, cooperation and effective use of digital technologies, and serves to the development of their professional-intellectual potential.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmedov, Y. O. (2025). Improving methodological approaches to organizing independent learning activities of students in the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. *Mug'allim hm zliksiz bilimlendiriw ilmiy-metodik journal*, (4), 116–123.
2. Mirsanov, U. M. (2023). Improving the methodology of teaching programming technologies in the system of continuous education. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc) dissertation abstract. Chirchiq. 76 p.
3. Yakovleva, V. N. (2017). **Functions, principles and means of managing students' independent learning activities in the process of their foreign language education at the university.** *Education in the 21st Century: Problems and Prospects*, 57–59.
4. Савицкий Ю. А. и др. Системный подход к самостоятельной работе обучающихся //Наука. Техника. Технологии (политехнический вестник). – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 445-448.